

PHILOSOPHICAL INVESTIGATION OF TECHNOLOGY AND ITS EFFECT ON HUMAN AND ARCHITECTURE

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ABSTRACT

There are many factors contributing in emergence of an architectural works including form, content, performance and technology. Form means the shape and geometry, content refers to theoretical foundations of a work, performance signifies efficiency and utilization of space and technology includes machines, tools and manufacturing method. Technology involves both materialistic elements and human activities. Since human behavior is affected by the surrounding atmosphere while forming a part of their identity, therefore, technology affects human and their identity as a part of environment. In the current article, the definition of technology, its views and its effects on the environment and architectural spaces were examined. In addition, the similarities and differences between modern and traditional technology and each effect on architectural space and human were analyzed. Finally, a strategy was proposed for appropriate application of modern technology in Iranian architecture.

KEYWORDS

Architecture, identity, traditional technology, modern technology.

1. INTRODUCTION

Contributing factors in forming any architectural work include content, performance, form and technology. Technology involves the thought about construction method, process, materials and building systems. Culture and content are internal to a work (which include concepts and connotations) originated from beliefs, philosophical foundations of society and the architect. Therefore, one of the main elements for creating an architectural work is technology.

In dictionaries, technology refers to a technical instrument for achieving scientific goals and in more recent definitions, the term refers to the fact that technology should not be limited and it should be regarded as integrated with instruments and machines. However, by reflecting on scientific and philosophical texts about technology, it is indicated that technology incorporates a wider range including the perspective toward the subject, process, method, results and consequences that in architecture it encompasses thoughts, theoretical underpinnings, design method and procedure, construction, materials, instruments, machines and finally the ultimate work. Thus, both materialistic elements and human activities are involved in this process resulting in creating architectural works.

As confirmed by behavioral and psychological sciences, the environment and its parts affect human behavior, actions and reactions while forming a part of human identity. In traditional architecture, technology developed in a gradual process along with architecture, culture and social and economic situations and is applied in a melted way in architecture. Practically, it is not possible to make a clear-cut distinction between architecture and technology. Hence, in any

principle-oriented society, especial thoughts and beliefs should contribute to their characteristics and utilize them.

2. WHAT IS TECHNOLOGY?

Undoubtedly, one of the most important and primary concepts in the philosophy of technology is its definition. One of the most important approaches in defining technology is based on Wingensten' view known as Definition in General terms. As we know, Wingensein is against essence-based tradition of philosophy history that defines an object with its essence and nature. He believes that one should get rid of comprehensively impeding definition based on nature and one should deal with the application of concepts. Therefore, if we want to know what technology or art is, we should search in various languages to see what applied meanings they have and how they are used.

Despite all this, whether in nature-based or non-natural definitions are software-based or sometimes hardware-based. In the hardware-based view about technology, it deals with creating tools and instruments for making our life more efficient and convenient. Software-based definition is, however, deals primary with thought and idea that is behind the tools. In the history of technology philosophy, hardware-based view has privilege over software-based ideas.

However, if we want to have a comprehensive definition of technology, we should say that technology is a set of information, instruments and techniques originated from practical science and experience used in design, production, and application of products, processes, systems and services. Unlike the primary supposition about technology as an instrument, technology could not be merely an instrument as some scholars' propagated technology in different areas such as thought, process, effect and results and some other scholars believe in a nature for technology that is different from technology. The relationship between human and technology has long been one of the main issues discussed in this area. According to some philosophers, technology has a neutral definition and has different values depending on the way it is used. That is, they do not believe in natural value for it and only consider agent factors in valuing technology. Compared to them, there is another group believing in natural value for technology and some others attribute some flaws and inefficiencies for the nature of technology (AbbasaliShahroudi, 1383). Hence, here are some definitions and views about technology:

With the emergence of technology philosophy, most of the authors wrote about the social effects of technology and its social structure. This type of contribution focusing on the relation between technology and social structure, can be called as philosophy about technology. In his study about the forming process of technology philosophy, Carl Mitcham identified four main approaches about technology.

1. technology as objects (search for the nature of technological devices)
2. technology as recognition (in epistemological view)
3. technology as reactions (around methodological issues)
4. technology as volition, (Teleological, ethical, aesthetical considerations) (Ali Zare Mirk Abad, Hedgier view about technology, Faculty of new sciences and technologies, University of Tehran)

Hart Davidson defined technology as a set of creations, cultural beliefs, experiences and contexts that include production. It also includes consumption, distribution and design which he considers for producing some cultural conditions.

He defined technology as “technology has been used since the 17th century for describing systematic study of arts or period of especial arts”. The Greek root for this word is Teknologia meaning a systematic behavior and its Greek etymology means art and industry. In the early 18th century, the natural definition of technology was a description of arts while in the mid-19th century, it meant empirical arts. In Oxford English Dictionary, technologist is a person who is solved in technology, a person who deals with study, work of art and instruments. He continued to note that in the second international dictionary (1909), the term technology means an industrial science or a systematic knowledge of industrial arts, especially for important products. However, in the third international dictionary (1961), the definition of technology is as follows: a set of applied tools by people for presenting their goals considering their culture.

However, it seems that the definition is too trivial. Some of the most confidentially new technologies should modify spiritual and psychological conditions. Many scholars maintained that the above-mentioned definitions are insufficient. Social scientists also insist that a practical, accurate and controllable definition should be proposed. Bernard Gordan believes that technology is considered as any systematically practical knowledge that is based on experience or practical theory and could be manifested in production frameworks and organizations or machines (Mohsen Vafamehr, 1386).

Martin Hydeger is among few philosophers who reflected on technology going beyond the surface while trying to discover the “dominant spirit in technology” and existential foundations. In 1954, in his article titles as “questioning technology”, he dealt with this issue trying to propose it as a human instrument through criticizing the common perspective technology. By noting that “the nature of technology is never a technological issue”, he attempted to distinguish the nature of technology from its examples and appearances. In his speech, he clarified the relation between technology and truth considering it as a “way for discovering truth, a discovery that could change human and everything will be as a source for saving for him”.

The common interpretation from technology: “technology as an instrument” is the starting point for discussion is provided with common and general interpretation from technology”. Hydeger noted in the beginning of “questioning technology”: “one says technology is a means for an end” another person may say “technology is a human activity”. These two definitions are related to each other since assigning a goal, supplying and applying suitable means are human activity”. Hydeger called this common definition of technology as “instrumental and human based technology”. The basis for this immature definition goes back to the fact that “technology” is made by human who created it for achieving their goals. That is why Hydeger considers this definition as “human-based and subjective”.

Understanding this issue requires a distinctive perception depicted by Hydeger between “accurate” or true and factual. He believed that any factual issue is necessarily accurate and true but any accurate issue is not necessarily factual. He regarded this definition of technology as accurate (true) through which one should go for factual definition of technology.

Hydeger distinguished between “specifying issues related to a topic” and “revealing a subject: accurate issue (accurate and true definition of a subject) addresses the issues related to it that are not natural and internal to the nature. He talks about this issue and specifies them while “factual

issue” deals with the subject itself (not the surrounding issues) and reveals the subject itself. He also believed that instrumental definition of technology does not reveal the nature of this phenomenon and merely talks about the related issues. According to Dan Idy: “accurate issue only has a limited meaning that is only in comparison with an aspect or a part of a larger whole...” (Zamani,2000).

3. THE EFFECT OF TECHNOLOGY ON NATURE AND ENVIRONMENT

During human life, technology has been one of the most unique receptions, attempts and searches that created a strong bond in various layers and angles of life and changing appearances of life which is, according to scientists, bidirectional. However, during different periods and various stages of social, cultural, political and economic evolution of societies, there were changes in this bond but never distorted (Vafamehr,2007).

It is said that recent information and new technologies are becoming common and human has to continue learning new theories and methods. Some individuals even argue that human has cultural delay in his attempt for applying new technologies and adapting with it. They hold that social changes are not able to cope with new technologies and humans will be conducive to self-alienation in an alienated world which is dehumanized. Even some people argue that modern technology leads to dehumanization or machining human. Technology abundance surrounds human while threatening the basis of humanity. Technology resulted in losing emotional and intuitive aspect of human relation and even arts are becoming technological and the distinctions between real and computer-made works are lost (Mohsen Vafamehr, 1386).

As mentioned earlier, Hydeger noted that “as long as we consider technology as an instrument, we will be captured in technology dominance and therefore, we will be unaware of the nature of technology” (Hydeger,1994, p. 27). In his view, technology has aggressive characteristics: aggression toward nature as changing it. Technology views nature as a source for raw materials and energy and requires change in shape, organizing and using it (VahidGhobadian, 2003).

With an irrational desire, technology asks nature to be mere producer and the source of energy. This is a kind of invitation to aggression. As technology should lead to change in the nature, it will also change in behavior and motivation in human and society. Modern human is a technological human which is different from human in the past. Since the nature of technology is aggressive, hence, modern human is captured by technology. In fact, the aggressions to nature gathers human for discipline and organizing the source of saving (nature) (Hydeger, 1996).

In the following, a brief description of the effects of technology on culture, environment and employment is noted:

1. Culture:

After industrial revolution, technology increasingly started to emerge and progress in different communities. Here, the term technocracy was proposed. In a technocratic society, instruments play a key role in all issues of the society especially the culture and all of the social evolutions and conditions should be, to a large extent, dependent on the needs and regulations of technology. By the emergence of technocracy, the collapse of ethical system and integrated thinking was facilitated and technocracy gave an answer for all of the human expectations, knowledge, and information whether about nature or spirit of human. After a while, the context for technopoly was provided. By the emergence of technopoly or monopoly of technology, one of the world

views of technology and custom and culture should be omitted. Technology proposes new definitions for religion, family, art, politics, history, truth, personal issues and other key words in life. Today, human is living in a world in which every second is witnessing a new event. It is a world full of wonders. It is a world in which technology advancement has been replaced with human advancement (according to Francis Bacon). It is a world in which removing blissfulness is not the end, but the final end is coordination with the expectations and desires of technology.

2. Environment:

With the progress in technology, there are a daily-increasing number of environmental risks. One could refer to many types of risks: air pollution (greenhouse effect), water pollution, increase in oceans temperatures, and life destruction in them, other pollutions such as wastes, and sound pollution, soil quality reduction due to frequent farming, chemical fertilizers and jungle destruction which is becoming faster with technology. In such cases, by using technological solutions, it is possible to minimize the damages. Using the best resources, finding a substitution for natural materials, etc. could help human as a dominant creature on the earth to save life.

3. Employment:

One of the continuous discussions around technology is about its effects on employment. Direct consequences of manufacturing technology progress is saving labor force and the unemployment is manifested in the society when unemployed people cannot find a job anywhere (Vafamehr, 2007).

4. THE EFFECT OF TECHNOLOGY ON ARCHITECTURE

Architecture is a term for which many definitions have been propose during recent years. Talking about architecture require knowing its boundaries. Here, some scholars' views are presented in this regard:

Lokobozieh:

Life machine, William Cortis: three dimensional definition of human behavior, Vitrovoice, believes in three areas of architecture including building art, clock construction and machine making (Hamidreza Ansari, 2006). According to Norman Foster, "architecture is not something in the critique's mind; architecture is about real life and people, about accommodating people and supplying their needs". MisVandrohe: "architecture is only the time desire for a lively changeable space. It is true that architecture is based on absolute facts, but its main job is meaning dominance. Architecture is time volition changed into space. Alive and new." ZahaHadid: "new architecture is not a limited system of spaces, we are living in a 360 degree world, I believe in open systems, infinity, no limitation, not closed communities" (Sanan, 2006).

With the brief look, it is identified that there is no consensus on the definition of architecture and its nature. However, how architecture is formed is one of the main issues in great architects' minds. One of its foundations is the first house built by human. The earliest idea is attributed to Vitrovoce. In his texts, he considers achieving a discipline in human made products not as a result of human logic, but his imitation of the nature and human body brings about such discipline (Ansar, 2006).

Gradually, technological progress caused new methods to be created so that buildings will not be limited only to building materials. Therefore, architecture was born from its origin, that is, technology.

In the world in which human is now living, technology is one the most effective issues. Architecture is not an exception. After technology entrance to architectural world, basic changes in architecture occurred and evolved every day after technology. The architecture for each period of time could be considered as the representative of people life in that period since it is an artistic phenomenon that has more limitations for changes compared to other arts. Economics, time and place are involved in shaping any architecture. An Architecture event is the result of coordination of a set of building characteristics. Lack of attention to these characteristics could change the quality of architecture as a thoughtful and artistic product (Mohsen Vafamehr, 1386). However, unfortunately, fast entrance of various technologies and change in life style caused change in the view to life and creation of architectural art. Industrials products and materials created a huge revolution providing architects with a wide range of facilities. The possibility for using technology paved the way for constructing new buildings. Architects, designers and constructors used knowledge, experience and new measurement possibilities in order to realize the dream for creating huge buildings (Hashemzadeh, 2001, p. 26). For instance, Santiago Kalatra tried to use modern technological possibilities to create works that were impossible in the past.

It seems that the most important change in this period was the emergence of electronic science, information technology and information and a phenomenon called computer. "The phenomenon (in) directly helps the method and processto create an architectural space along with fast transfer of experiences" (Baghahi, 2001, p. 20). The exchange between experience and industry changed the way of life and jobs in all countries affecting the cultures. Applying modern technologies has caused architecture to be more independent of environmental elements in order to make architecture more similar to machine. "In such case, architecture cannot act as a structure for changing technology direction to a human concept with temporal value" (Shahroudi, 2004). With the development of technology and more possibilities for architects to use new materials and spaces, gradually the atmosphere for architectural buildings is changing. Once adobe and brick were the only materials and the architects had to construct thick walls to be able to tolerate the loads. However, in the contemporary world and with smaller and lighter materials, forming spaces has changed. Today, instead of thick brick walls that were heavy and took a lot of space, it is possible to use light and thin wall and separate the internal space by new materials such as plastic, opaque glasses, etc. Using new materials has many advantages and only a few of them are suggested. However, using these materials around the globe has made all of the architectures similar to each other regardless of the climate, culture, etc. For example, there are many buildings in Iran made by materials that are not compatible with the climate, culture and characteristics of Iran. In Tehran, regardless of the risk for earthquake, sun, and hot weather, keeping privacy and neighboring, glass-made buildings are built as an imitation for modern architecture and use of high technology while this high technology could be used in a more appropriate way. For instance, light, resistant, unbreakable, insulated and other characteristics of new materials are recommended.

As mentioned above, when it comes to modern technology and its entrance to architecture, what come to our mind are computer and its effect on the architecture of the world. In art and especially in architecture in which the abstract mind should become concrete, the artist or the designer should be able to make what s/he has in their mind understandable for others. For many years, architects have used many instruments and methods for transferring their ideas. Among the

examples, one could refer to designing with pen (S6), two-dimensional maps, three-dimensional pictures (perspective) and three-dimensional models (Maquette).

In these methods, it was not possible have three-dimensional view of all angles of architectural spaces. However, in recent years with the advent of graphic computer technology, many changes occurred in this context and the positive results made it spread all over the world. By this system, the architect is enabled to easily achieve all of the angles of his work through 3D fixed and motion pictures of computer (Animation) without drawing many hand-made paintings.

In the following, some advantages of applying computer in designing process are proposed:

1. Design, control, and modifying the design by the designer with the minimum time and maximum facilities in comparison with traditional visual systems.
2. Ability for transferring the exact idea and other technological issues.
3. Ability to create 3D databases used up to the final stages of implementation.
4. Precisely introducing the graphic design in order to present in various places.
5. Speed and precision in measurement

Using this system not only brings about different and easy methods for presenting architectural designs, but also, different kinds of software help the architects and designers to measure and design in the sense that most of the modern designs are not possible without computer measurement.

Using new technologies should not cause the architects to apply any technology and make them common in the world without paying attention to the conditions of the country such as cultural and climatological requirements. Now that humanity is facing wide possibilities of technology and industry in communications era, it is better to use it for gathering experts and architects and provide it for others (Vafamehr, 2007).

5. TRADITIONAL AND MODERN TECHNOLOGY IN ARCHITECTURE

Form is defined as the geometry and the shape of work and performance includes users and utilizations in architectural spaces. Technology includes the process of construction, thought about construction method and materials, techniques and building systems.

Culture and content for a non-physical theme involving proposed concepts and meanings in parts and whole work which originates from culture, history, beliefs and philosophical foundations of society and architect. Therefore, one of the main elements in each architectural work is technology. In the past and today used two types of technology namely, traditional and modern technology. Traditional technologies are rarely devised, but modern technology has always been disciplined. Methods in traditional technologies could be clarified but are not formulated such as principles for various needs and people. However, main theories of modern technologies depend on their needs.

Nevertheless, in addition to the afore-mentioned differences, the method for applying and engaging modern and traditional architecture has evolved and modern technologies lead to change in identity and content of spaces and elements of architecture (Shahroudi, 2007).

Thus, in any society that relied on principles, thoughts and beliefs should specify the way for applying technology with regard to their characteristics. In the following, two characteristics of modern and traditional technologies are examined and compared:

Booming traditional technology and universality of modern technology

- Traditional technology is applied in its local territory and is formed based on different requirements appropriate for local position and development if modern technologies is propagated in the whole world and impose itself on different communities.
- The hand-made nature of traditional technology and machine-based nature of modern technology:
- Traditional technology is manifested by direct engagement of human in three areas of thought, process and effect, but modern technology deals with machines and human is omitted in many cases.
- Interaction with environment by traditional technology and its correspondence with environment by modern technology:
- Traditional technology is basically according to human interaction with the environment and it is the result of an internal relation with environment. However, modern technology requires the environment to be at its service and uses it as a source of energy.

Simplicity of traditional technology and complexity of modern technology:

- Traditional technology is represented in a simple form in traditional communities. The method for thinking, performance and the final result of works are simple but modern technology is complex due to meeting various needs.
- Individual construction in traditional technology and mass construction of modern technology:
- Traditional technology tries to meet each need and avoids mass construction for unknown people. On the other hand, it was not possible to have mass construction in traditional technology, but modern technology facilitated mass production and tries to produce in large number in order to reduce costs and meeting the needs.

The limitations of traditional and variety of modern technology:

- Traditional technology attempted to meet the needs of societies given different limitations and dominance of thoughts. However, modern technology tries to create more consumption and need considering characteristics such as consumerism or competition rising.
- Increasing sacredness in traditional technology and anti-sacredness in modern technology:
- In traditional communities, religious and worldview-based teachings were controlling and guiding ideology that specified the use of instruments. In other words, technology was at the service of ideology while in modern communities, there is neither sacred technology nor any taboo. Technique does not worship anything and does not respect anything. Rather, it is a sacred entity dominating human life (Shahroudi, 2007).

6. THE EFFECT OF TECHNOLOGY ON IRANIAN ARCHITECTURE

As pointed out, technology in dictionaries refer to technical instrument for achieving scientific goals and also more recent definitions of technology connote the same meaning that it should not be limited and considered the same as instrument and machine.

At the first glance, technology appears to be the same as instruments and machines; however, as mentioned earlier, by reflecting on scientific and philosophical texts about technology, it is established that technology encompasses wider continuum including thought and perspective toward subject, process and method and final result which is applied in architecture, thought, theoretical underpinning, method and process for design and construction, materials, instruments, machines and the final work. Therefore, it includes materialistic elements and involves human activities both of which lead to creating an architectural work. As confirmed by behavioral and psychological sciences, environment and its elements affect behaviors, actions and reactions of human shaping a part of human identity. Hence, technology and its elements affect human and their identity as an environmental factor.

In traditional architecture, technology grew in a steadily continuous process along with architecture, culture and social and economic conditions and resolved in architecture, thereby there is no practical distinction between architecture and technology.

However, after industrial revolution in the west and dramatic progress in science and technology and western society adaptation with modern technology and the correspondence between technology and dominant culture in the west, western architecture is in a good position in the world with regard to cultural, social, political and economic conditions. However, given the underdevelopment in many scientific, economic and technological areas, Iran has become an importing country that imports science and technology. Ties between Iranian culture and architecture as well as modern technology in an incomplete way, there have/ been some abnormalities in architecture and culture. Despite that, given contemporary needs of Iranian communities that should obviate the need for using complex and high technology, there must be some philosophical basis for modern technology and its effects on architectural atmosphere (Shahroudi,2007).

With respect to the effect of technology on architecture, as mentioned earlier, if technology and architecture are corresponding with each other, the effect is intangible, but if architecture is behind technology, definitely the effect will be tangible when they are going to correspond and lead to changes in architecture.

In the architecture of our country, as long as technology and architecture are corresponding, the trend was intangibly going forward and whenever there was no correspondence, we faced changes in Iranian architecture.

Past Iranian architecture relied on boom and boundaries. The type of technology was hidden and even in the last 4 hundred years, it was the only industry of the country. With respect to construction, modulation was used (both in construct, elements and materials), but view toward modulation was qualitative and is not considered as a metric and quantitative issue as it is today. Where architecture was correspondent with technology, in fact, there was not goal except for enhancing quality. Technology in itself has nature, creativity, product and dependence that impose limits on it. Areas of science were limited in the past, therefore, architect relies on architecture, technology and creates works, that is, as long as there was no need for industries and

new sciences, the architect was self-relying in methodology, heating, cooling, lights, and acoustics and we were pioneer in a comprehensive architecture. Today, with the emergence of new science, we are following the west and our architecture is emptied from its existence through receiving these sciences imperfectly. Adapting expertise with architecture cannot be perfect. The technological architecture in contemporary era is extremist moving toward machinism as we could see a tower construction in Dubai equipped with electromotor and powerful technique and it is in contradiction with the issue of resistance. Attention to resistance was fundamental in our traditional technology. Booming and principles proposed by the late Pirnia, as architecture based on boom having highest feedback with minimum energy. If our architecture is in correspondence with the needs of the time and was formed with technological view, it would have had a different form today. The problem is that, on one hand, we could not explore this technology and, on the other hand, we tried to apply the modern technology of the world without considering cultural aspects of societies. Thus, the technology is condemned to death, not success. The bond between time requirements and past logic which was boom is the medium solution for the problem (Vafamehr, 2009).

Generally, fundamental thoughts of current Iranian architecture that is concomitant with our time are as follows:

The history of emergence is the late Qajar period and is about fast transfer of thoughts and ideas since modern society is based on transfer speed for basic information and information exchange leads to balance in culture and architectural model.

Tehran as the capital of Iran and connecting point of Iran to Europe is a complex responsibility in expanding architecture. The origins of Iranian modern architecture are transferring deceptive culture of the west to the introvert society of Iran and accordingly, it was destroyed considering new technologies around cities. Therefore, organic textures changed into geometrical forms. In this period, western formula is implemented by importing possibilities and technologies. Meanwhile, the second origin of this period is economic utilization in architecture. Perhaps, it is possible to consider the medium period of Iranian modern architecture as the first time in which architecture was introduced as an economic good and relies on principles of modern architecture such as removing details of architecture not as a reflective tool for culture, but as an economic product.

The presence of technology in different areas such as forming initial thought, process for evolving thought, design and construction process, and utilization of works take various forms. This presence has different effects on architecture. Today, by looking at technology in Iranian architecture, we see that there is quantitative and physical perspective while always ignoring non-physical aspects. As mentioned earlier, some scholars consider technology as mere instrument which is neutral and ineffective. On one hand, technological thought for contemporary human is after industrial revolution that is the result of changes in theoretical and practical aspects. On the other hand, as confirmed by environmental psychology, all of the environmental elements affect human. Thus, the presence of thought, process and technological works is not ineffective.

Modern technology in different areas of contemporary Iranian architecture affects the process of design and construction and represents its effects in architecture spaces, but it ignored its effects as it views it as a neutral instrument while the effect of modern technology thought on architecture training is revealed. Therefore, discussions about technology and construct in some works are proposed in contemporary architecture which is not the reason for accepting theoretical

foundations, but it is an emphasis on how the correspondence between technology and construct is made. The goal is to find the way for achieving such destination (Shahroudi, 2007).

7. CONCLUSION

Architecture and technology are two different principles with regard to how to view the issues and how to meet their needs. What is absolute is that technology is not merely an instrument for higher efficiency, but it is important and effective. Technology affects all aspects of human life and changes values and people perspectives. In fact, the nature of technology determines human view toward human and social values. New values are created that are different from the values of human in the past.

Positive and negative effects of technology in architecture are similar to that of culture, economy and society. Using new materials and creating new computer systems and software dependent on different methods for presenting architectural designs are among the positive effects of technology.

Like other contexts, emergence of new technologies in architecture had negative impacts. One of the consequences for technology progress is having monotonous architecture and urbanization in different parts of the country in contemporary era while in the past, the form of buildings, districts and cities showed the cultural characteristics and local preferences of inhabitants. These characteristics are ruined and the structure of cities and villages are away from their culture and history while architecture is deeply connected to culture and its differences. Regardless of destroying local identity of architecture in contemporary Iran, another problem is misuse of technology in biological environment.

A glance at local technology of Iran suggests recognizing environmental characteristics, especially climatological features of Iran that show the thoughtfulness of our ancestors for using the nature as much as possible and address the climatological and environmental problems (Chamani, 2007).

Local industries and techniques have grown in a steady way along with architecture, culture, social and economic conditions and is practically a distinction between architecture and technology. New technologies propose an international model for construction. As a result, due to discordance between boom and location, it has negative effects on nature. Moreover, given the topic, the problem of today architecture is internationalization of technology. For this reason, today architecture do not have the quality of older one since they are away from context and boom. Therefore, for having architecture simultaneous with progress and use of technology and advanced movement, there must be an answer. Attention should be given to using new technology, tradition, custom, culture, climate and people desire and distinctions.

In fact, the history of civilized environment and context of a society is defined by form, index and boundaries of architecture. Mere technological view without social consideration leads to marginalizing architecture. In fact, the ideology of countries differs. A new technology cannot happen without considering social, cultural and local context since it will become unstable and fake. The capacity of a social-political discipline in a society is the rudimentary context for accepting and using technology (Diba, 2009).

Given all of the aforementioned issues and the fact that human is perfectionist and it is not possible to have perfection without achieving new science. Therefore, human tries to gain new

science. In this effort and through creation of complex technology, sometimes it is impacted by its product and human is turned into a metamorphosed entity. Culture forgets its past and it at the service of technology. Although Hydeger talked against technology, he still is not against it: "technology is the destination of our era and by destination, we mean inevitably unchangeable route" (Hydeger, 1994: p. 20). However, the nature of technology should be identified through deeper investigation. He believed that the way to deal with modern technology is achieved by appealing to original and spiritual thought and having an artistic view.

REFERENCES

- [1] Aydi, Dan (1998); "Art and technology: epistemological philosophy of Hydeger in technology", translator, ShapourEtemad, Tehran: NashreMarkaz.
- [2] Jafari Najaf Abadi, Atefeh (2001), "the role of boom-based technologies in the quality of residential spaces"
- [3] Chamani, Malihe (2007), "boom-based constructs in stable architecture", first conference in construct and architecture.
- [4] Zamani, Ali, Amir Abbas (2000) "the nature of technology in Hydeger's view", Mofid Quarterly, no. 23, pp. 197-222.
- [5] Shayanfar, Shiva (2008), "the nature of technology and its role architecture training", set of the third articles for architecture training conference, University of Tehran.
- [6] Shahroudi, Abbasali, Golabchi, Mahmoud (2007); "technology and architecture: comparing the effects of traditional and modern technology on human and technology". The first conference for construct and architecture.
- [7] Ali Zamani, Amirabbas (2000), "the nature of technology in Hydeger's view". Mofid Quarterly, no. 23.
- [10] Vafamehr, Mohsen, Majidi, Sayna (2007), "technology and cultural identity trap in architecture", industrial development technology quarterly, 5th, no. 11.
- [11] Vafamehr, Mohsen, Mohebi far, Hazhir (2007), "the effect of technology on human life". First conference in construct and architecture.
- [12] Hydeger, Martin (2007), "Questioning technology", translator, ShapourEtemad, Book "technology philosophy", NashreMarkaz.
- [13] Zare Mirk Abad, Ali, "Hydeger view about technology", facultyof new sciences and technologies, University of Tehran.
- [14] Especial Manzar Monthly, no. 4. p. 80-81. Bahman, 2009.